

Zoonotic Diseases: Causes, Symptoms, Diagnosis, Treatment and Influence of Climate

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045097>

Article Received: 21-July-2025, Revised: 11-August-2025, Accepted: 01-September-2025, Online First: 03-September-2025

ABSTRACT:

Climate change is real and here. It has a wide range of effects on the environment – increasing global temperatures & Extreme Weather Events (EWE) which in turn are impacting human health. Climate change is a potent factor that is emerging as a global risk by altering disease occurrence, transmission, virulence and pathogenicity of the pathogenic microbes. It affects the main determinants of the disease ecology such as host, pathogen, and environment. A lot of challenges are involved in diagnosis, treatment, and prevention strategies and this must be overcome. This paper specifically focuses on the Zoonotic diseases induced by climate change. This paper addresses the major area of climate change and lists major zoonotic diseases and its mechanism of transmission. Also offers the current treatment available and clinical correlation between symptoms and diagnostic methods. This paper concludes with broader requirement of further research and caution to be exercised during the application of the Symptom, Diagnosis, Treatment outlined in the treatment section of this paper.

Keywords: zoonotic diseases, Climate Change, infectious diseases

INTRODUCTION:

Climate change is a major threat to public health, with rising global temperatures leading to sea level rise, changes in the spread and risk of diseases, water & food insecurity and increased frequency and severity of Extreme Weather Events (EWE, mostly being flood due to sea level rise) (1,4). Emerging infectious Diseases (EIDs) are illnesses that are newly defined or have existed but are increasing in incidence or geographic range which poses a threat to the population, either in a particular area or globally. Conversely, Re-emerging infectious Disease (REID) are illnesses that existed in the past but reappear after they have been on a significant decline, and rapidly spread either in terms of incidence or to new geographical areas (3,5). Climate change, defined by the United Nations framework convention on climate change as “a change of climate which is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere, and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time period” (21). Nowadays, Zoonotic diseases are increasing in number. They are novel diseases acquired from animals. They have unique features and pose a great challenge to the

humankind. So, this paper gives a brief overlook at how climate change affects zoonotic diseases.

Climate Change:

Climates refer to long-term shifts in temperature and weather patterns, which are disrupting ecological systems worldwide leading to shift in the global distribution of pathogens hosts and disease reservoirs (27). Climate Change acts via so called the climate drivers. Climate change causes many changes in the environment such as El-Nino southern oscillations [ENSO], ocean acidification, sea level rise, increase in extreme weather events, melting of permafrost, etc. Caused by an increase in greenhouse gases, there is an increase in temperature, which causes melting of ice and glaciers and ocean acidification and extreme weather events. This causes flooding and sea level rise, affecting habitats. This change in habitat affects diseases.

Climate change and health:

Many diseases are aggravated by climate change while some are diminished. However, It was found that most diseases that were diminished by at least one hazard were at times aggravated by another and sometimes the same hazard. It is believed that a warming & unstable

climate is playing a role in driving the global emergence & redistribution of infectious diseases (12). Not only affecting the diseases, transmission and their causative organisms, but also affects the human behaviour and other demographic factors, which is also affected by a lot of factors, and it also gives rise to a lot of other factors. It increases the host susceptibility, host-pathogen interaction (mostly due to habitat destruction and exposure to contaminated transmitters) and the ability of the organisms (disease causers) to get transmitted and infect people (virulence) (1,4). It influences the hosts causing them to be more infectious. The adaptation of pathogen to one environmental stressor also primes them to withstand other adverse environments.

Climate change and population vulnerability:

Climatic hazards have also diminished human capacity to cope with pathogens by altering body conditions; adding stress from exposure to hazardous conditions; forcing people into unsafe conditions; damaging infrastructure, forcing exposure to pathogens and / or reducing access to medical care. Increase in carbon dioxide levels in atmosphere causes malnutrition as plants have no time to absorb nutrients. This malnutrition causes immune incompetency which allows a lot of zoonotic pathogens to infect humans as they lag only in fighting against human immune systems. Then they may confer ability to defeat human immune systems, therefore aiding epidemics and pandemics. Greenhouse gases can also cause respiratory problems which can add up to co-infection with a zoonotic pathogen, making them complex and difficult to treat. Same can occur to UV related cancer, which is caused as UV rays bypass the ozone layer because of holes. Stress, represented by the stress hormone cortisol, affects the immune system, so after EWE, with or without post-traumatic stress disorder, can increase vulnerability. Climate change may also provide certain features to diseases such as drug resistance, making them more powerful. They can cause acid rain, which again establishes food insecurity.

Zoonotic Diseases and Climate Change:

The causes of zoonotic diseases are urbanization, industrialization, Land use change, exploitation of forestry and wildlife, unsustainable utilization of natural resources, travel and transportation, climate change and agricultural intensification and destruction of wetlands and forests to compensate for the low agricultural productivity due to climate change. Land use change brings human and pathogens closer, thereby increasing the risk of zoonosis. A numerous outbreaks have been reported like Ebola, scrub typhus, Lyme disease, and malaria.

Many Zoonotic diseases found in ectothermic animals can defeat the human immunity but are not thermotolerant. When they acquire thermotolerance, they can affect people and cause diseases. This thermotolerance is promoted by climate change by an increase in temperature. Many new diseases are emerging from the wild due to deforestation and hunting of animals. The factors affecting spillover and outbreaks are Geographic range, Migration, Sociodemographic factors and events, Mutations, Species & Specificity. Then a zoonotic pathogen must cross the following barriers to affect humans and sustain in human population:

1. Ability and opportunity to infect an animal

Animals' dependency on natural resources is the main reason for propagation of this phase.

Climate change: Climate change affects this phase in the following ways:

- By increasing the temperature, it increases animals' visits to water resources.
- It increases the ability of pathogen to affect many organisms.
- By Extreme Weather Events, it leads to animal migration, which increases likelihood of infection.
- Physical Injury caused due to climate change can increase the risk of the animal getting infected.

2. Developing disease against animal's immune system

This phase is important as it helps the pathogen gain virulence.

Climate change: Climate change affects this phase through the following way:

- By inducing malnutrition through several factors, it decreases the ability of immune system to fight against infection.
- Climate change also increases the risk of co-infections, thus developing the virulence capacity of a non-virulent pathogen.

3. Transmission between the animals

This phase is a dormant phase. Many potent zoonotic diseases are present in this phase.

Climate change: Climate change affects this phase through the following way: By extreme weather events including drought, it brings animals closer and leads to transmission.

4. Ability and Opportunity to infect a human

This phase is also known as zoonosis. This phase is also important because it is the first stage of a zoonotic disease.

Climate change: Climate change affects this phase through the following ways:

- Climate change causes organisms to become thermo tolerant by increasing the ambient

temperatures, thus helping them defeat the body's response of fever due to which many diseases were unable to infect humans.

- Exploitation of animal resources and ecosystems for human purposes leads to animal migration to human land, thus increasing the risk of zoonosis.
- By extreme weather events, it brings humans and animals closer thus favouring zoonosis.
- By creating drought, it can lead to lack of water resources, bring animals and people together.

5. Fight against human immune system

This phase is important as it is the step where a disease stabilizes itself in a human body against immune system.

Climate Change: Climate Change affects this phase through

- By increasing the risk of co-infections, it reduces the ability of immune system to fight against them.
- Stress also plays a significant role in modulation of immune responses against diseases.
- By reducing the nutrients present in the food through increasing carbon dioxide levels, It causes malnutrition which can lead to decreased immune functioning.
- It can also cause an increase in virulence of organisms.

6. Transmission in human population

Transmission between human to human is a necessary to sustain in human population.

Climate change: Climate change affects this phase by the many ways. Some of the ways are:

- Through Extreme Weather Events, it causes crowding of people in rescue camps.
- Through increasing temperatures, It causes people to stay inside doors which promotes transmission between family members.
- By increasing disease prevalence, it leads to crowd up of people in healthcare facilities which can lead to hospital acquired infections.

Challenges:

Challenges posed by zoonotic diseases are listed below

- Diseases are affected by a lot of factors including climate change, and it involves multiple interactions (4).
- Climate change affects both people's immunity, susceptibility, pathogen's ability and availability (8).
- Cost is a great influencing factor (10) & Research is low and needs to be fuelled up.
- Surveillance tools must be developed, and diseases monitoring must be improved.

- Evidentiary database must be created and implemented, and attention must be paid to climate change.
- Large scale migration puts people at risk for zoonotic diseases.
- Emerging Drug-Resistance.
- New and previously unknown diseases that may or may not have known treatment regimens and prevention strategies.
- Malnutrition caused by climate change.
- Healthcare facilities are affected by climate change.
- Change in people's living conditions and lifestyle.

Solution and prevention

- Multidiscipline and multiplatform collaboration between researchers and healthcare providers, policymakers and businesspersons are needed to find solutions.
- Models must be developed to aid in the prediction and efforts must be made to minimize the effects of the upcoming or predicted climate change related disasters.
- Tracking and stimulation models must be in use for the effective planning.
- Developing notification systems which notify the individuals residing in the area which is forecasted to be affected by climate change.
- Diagnostics must be revolutionised for the proper identification of the disease- and disease-causing agent.
- treatment regimens and preventive strategies must be developed to fight against diseases.
- prevention of resistance due to inappropriate treatment is necessary.
- Use of Satellite imaging technology to find areas under risk for zoonotic diseases.
- Execution of Epidemiological analysis is a must to detect any epidemics.
- Weather forecast is necessary as a part of predicting any climate-based risks.
- Improvement of Healthcare sector so that it is resilient against extreme weather events and can treat a lot of patients.
- Development of Early warning systems are critical to ensuring preparedness.
- Solution is of two parts: adaptation and mitigation.
- Public health measures must be taken in order to prevent any disasters, and the people must take preventive measures.
- Public awareness is of utmost importance.

Treatment:

Table-I provides the detailed analysis of major Zoonotic Diseases and their cause, Transmission, Symptom, Diagnosis, Treatment & Challenges. The treatment suggested are preliminary and treatment shall also be covered based on symptoms, co-infections, travel history, test reports, radiology reports, age, sex, patient conditions, available infrastructure, etc. This table does not cover the risk assessment and drug induced side effects. Treatment plan shall also consider local medical

body or WHO or CDC guidelines. Due to human activities and effects of climate change, zoonotic diseases become more prevalent, frequent and deadly. Diseases, which are more virulent present in the wild, acquire features to attain thermotolerance and infect human populations. They have unique features, and their epidemics can be devastating. They have a sociodemographic and financial burden. While Extreme Weather Events affect healthcare sector, these diseases take advantage of them and quickly start an epidemic.

Table - I: Climate Change and Zoonotic Diseases: Cause, Transmission, Symptom, Diagnosis, Treatment & Challenges

S.NO	DISEASE	MICROBE	TRANSMISSION	NATURAL RESERVOIR	VACCINE AVAILABILITY	SYMPTOMS	DIAGNOSIS (EXCEPT CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS)	TREATMENT (EXCEPT SYMPTOMATIC TREATMENT)	PREVENTION	REFERENCE
1	ZIKA	ZIKA VIRUS	VECTOR(MOSQUITO-HUMAN-MOSQUITO), ZOOBOTIC, BLOOD TRANSFUSION, MOTHER TO BABY, SEXUAL	MONKEY, HUMANS, PRIMATES	NO	80% OF PEOPLE ARE ASYMPTOMATIC; FEVER, RED EYES, JOINT PAIN, HEADACHE, MACULOPAPULAR RASH;	NAAT, ANTI BODY DETECTION, ANTIGEN TEST, NEUTRALIZATION ASSAYS	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	(AVOIDING MOSQUITO BITES AND PREVENT CONTACT WITH MOSQUITOES) DEET & PICARDIN BASED MOSQUITO REPELLANTS, CLOTHING, MOSQUITO NETS	2,6,7,9,17,22,25
2	RIFT VALLEY FEVER	VIRUS	VECTOR, CONTACT WITH FLUIDS OR OF INFECTED ANIMALS, ZOOBOTIC	CATTLE	YES	FEVER, MUSCLE PAIN, HEADACHE, BACK PAIN, DIZZINESS, WEIGHT LOSS; LOSS OF SIGHT, CONFUSION, LIVER PROBLEMS, HEMORRHAGIC FEVER SYNDROME, MENINGOENCEPHALITIS, EYE INFECTION	NAAT, ANTI BODY DETECTION, ANTIGEN TEST	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	(AVOIDING MOSQUITO BITES) VACCINATING ANIMALS AGAINST DISEASE	2,6,22
3	NIPAH VIRUS	NIPAH VIRUS	ZOOBOTIC, EXPOSURE TO BODILY FLUIDS OF INFECTED PERSON(S)	FRUIT BATS, PIGS	NO	FEVER, COUGH, HEADACHE, SHORTNES S OF BREATH, CONFUSION; DIZZINESS, DROWSINESS; ENCEPHALITIS, SEIZURES	RT-PCR, ANTIBODY DETECTION	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	AVOIDING EXPOSURE TO BATS AND SICK PIGS AND THINGS PARTIALLY CONTAMINATED BY THEM	2,9,24
4	INFLUENZA/FLU	INFLUENZA VIRUS	RESPIRATORY DROPLETS, ZOOBOTIC S, CONTAMINATED SURFACE CONTACT	CATTLE, PIGS, AQUATIC BIRDS	YES	FEVER, RUNNY NOSE, SORE THROAT, MUSCLE PAIN, HEADACHE, COUGHING	RT-PCR, NAAT, ANTIGEN TESTING, RAPID MOLECULAR TESTING,	OSELTAMIVIR, BALOXAVIR, ZANAMIVIR, SUPPORTIVE CARE	HAND WASHING, FLU VACCINES, SOCIAL DISTANCING, LIMIT CONTACT WITH INFECTED, FOLLOW	4,22

						, FATIGUE; DIARRHOEA, VOMITING, TIREDNESS (EXTREME) ; PNEUMONIA; ACUTE RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME, MENINGITIS, ENCEPHALITIS, ASTHMA, CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES, SEPSIS, LYSIS OF CELLS;			HYGENIC PRACTISES, COVER YOUR NOSE AND MOUTH WHILE SNEEZING	
5	CAMPYLOBACTERIOSIS	CAMPYLOBACTER SPP.	ZOOONOTIC, CONTAMINATED FOOD AND WATER, BATHING	POULTRY, CATTLE, PIGS, SHEEP, CATS, DOGS, OSTRICHES	NO	DIARRHOEA, GASTROENTERITIS, FEVER, VOMITING, GUILLAIN-BARRE SYNDROME; PAIN, NAUSEA	ISOLATION FORM STOOL SAMPLE, STOOL CULTURE, GRAM STAINING OF STOOL SAMPLE, PCR, ANTIGEN TESTING	ANTIBIOTICS, SUPPORTIVE CARE	AVOID CONTACT WITH INFECTED, SANITATION AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS, PROPER COOKING PRACTISES, NEVER CONSUME RAW MILK PRODUCTS INCLUDING MILK, BOILING WATER, HAND HYGIENE, FOOD HYGIENE, WASH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES THROUGHLY	4,13, 22
6	MENANGLER	MENANGLER PARARUBULAVIRUS	ZOOONOTIC	FRUIT BATS, PIGS	NO	FEVER, CHILLS, RIGORS, SWEATS, MALAISE, HEADACHE , RED SPOTTED RASH	HISTOPATHOLOGY EXAMINATION, MENANGLER VIRUS NEUTRALIZATION TEST, MENANGLER VIRUS ISOLATION, ANTIGEN TESTING, ANTIBODY DETECTION	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	AVOID CONTACT WITH INFECTED ANIMALS, STANDARD HYGIENE AND SANITATION PRACTISES MUST ALSO BE FOLLOWED	11
7	LEPTOSPIROSIS	LEPTOSPIRA SPP	ANIMAL FAECES OR URINE CONTACT, ZOOONOTIC, CONTAMINATED WATER, BATHING	RODENTS	YES	HEADACHE , MUSCLE PAIN, FEVER, JAUNDICE, BLEEDING IN THE LUNGS, WEIL'S DISEASE, KIDNEY FAILURE, SEVERE PULMONARY HAEMORRHAGIC SYNDROME, SKIN RASH(RARE), CONJUNCT	ANTIBODY TESTING, DNA DETECTION, IMAGING, BLOOD AND URINE TESTS, DETECTION OF BACTERIA IN BLOOD AND CEREBROSPINAL FLUID	DOXYCYCLINE, PENICILLIN, CEFTRIAXONE, AMOXICILLIN, AMPICILLIN	PPE, HYGIENE MEASURES, PROPHYLAXIS, AVOID CONTACT WITH INFECTED ANIMALS, CLOTHING, AVOID WATER (WHICH COULD BE CONTAMINATED), DRINK ONLY PURE, FILTERED AND BOILED WATER, COVER CUTS AND WOUNDS WITH WATERPROOF DRESSING,	4, 12, 18, 19

						IVAL SUFFUSION , PHOTOPHO BIA, COUGH, ABDOMINA L PAIN AND VOMITING, CHOLECYS TITIS, PANCREAT ITIS, MENINGITI S, MYOCARDI TIS(RARE), LIVER FAILURE, MELENA, BRUISES, STOMACH BLEEDING			CLEAN AND DISINFECT SURFACES	
8	SALMO NELLOS IS	SALMO NELLA SPP	CONTAMIN ATED FOOD AND WATER, ZOOBOTIC	CONTAMINA TED FOOD	YES	FOOD POISONING , DIARRHEA, FEVER, ABDOMINA L CRAMPS, VOMITING, ENTERITIS, TYPHOID FEVER, IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROM E, INFLAMMA TORY BOWEL DISEASE, CHILLS, HEADACHE , STOMACH ACHE, NAUSEA	STOOL TEST, BLOOD TESTS, URINE TEST, WOUND(ABS CESS) TEST	CIPROFLOXA CIN, CEFTRIAOX ON, TRIMETHOP RIM- SULFAMETH OXAZOLE, AZITHROMY CIN, SUPPORTIVE CARE	PROPER WASHING, PREPARATION, COOKING OF FOOD, VACCINE, FOOD HYGIENE	4, 3, 22,20,13
9	SHIGA TOXIN PRODUC ING E.COLI	ESCHE RICHIA COLI	ZOOBOTIC, CONTAMIN ATED FOOD AND WATER, DIRECT CONTACT, CONTAMIN ATED SURFACE CONTACT	CATTLE	NO	GASTROEN TERITIS, ENTEROCO LITIS, BLOODY DIARRHOE A; HEMOLYTI C UREMIC SYNDROM E; STOMACH CRAMPS, FEVER, VOMITING, DIARRHOE A	STOOL CULTURE, BLOOD CULTURE, URINE CULTURE	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	COOKING FOOD PROPERLY, AVOID UNPASTEURIZE D DRINKS, HAND HYGIENE DURING FOOD PREPARATION, SERVING AND EATING, PURIFY AND BOIL WATER BEFORE DRINKING AND AVOID DRINKING OR BEING IN CONTACT WITH CONTAMINATE D WATER, WASH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES PROPERLY	4
10	YERSINI OSIS	YERSI NIA ENTER COLI TICA, YERSI NIA PSEUD OTUBE RCULO SIS	ZOOBOTIC, FOOD BORNE, HUMAN TO HUMAN, WATERBOR NE, BLOOD TRANSFUSI ON, DIRECT	PIG, COW, GOAT, INTESTINAL TRACTS OF NUMEROUS MAMMALS, AVIAN SPECIES, COLD- BLOODED SPECIES,	NO	ENTEROCO LITIS, ILEITIS, BLOODY DIARRHOE A, FEVER, APPENDICI TIS, LYMPHAD ENOPATHY	STOOL TESTING, ISOLATION OF ORGANISM FROM BILE, BLOOD, CEREBROSPI NAL FLUID, MESENTERIC LYMPH	AMINOGLYC OSIDES, THIRD- GENERATION CEPHALOSPO RINS, FLUOROQUIN OLONES, TETRACYCLI NES, TRIMETHOPR	AVOIDING UNPASTEURIZE D PRODUCTS, BEING CAREFUL WITH ANIMAL WASTE, COOKING FOOD PROPERLY, PREVENTING	4

			TRANSMISSION	TERRESTRIAL AND AQUATIC NICHES			NODES, PERITONEAL FLUID, STOOL, A THROAT SWAB, WOUND CULTURE	IM-SULFAMETH OXAZOLE	CROSS-CONTAMINATION, WASHING YOUR HANDS	
11	GIARDIASIS	GIARDIA DUODENALIS	FAECAL-ORAL ROUTE, PERSON TO PERSON TRANSMISSION, ZOOONOTIC, BATHING, CONTACT WITH CONTAMINATED SURFACE	BEAVERS, DOGS, CATS, PRIMATES	NO	10% OF INFECTED HAVE NO SYMPTOMS ; DIARRHOEA, ABDOMINAL PAIN, WEIGHT LOSS, VOMITING, BLOOD IN STOOLS, GAS, ABDOMINAL CRAMPS, NAUSEA, VOMITING, WEIGHT LOSS, FATIGUE	STOOL TESTING, ANTIGEN DETECTION, MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION OF STOOLS, ANTIBODY TESTING, MICROSCOPY WITH DIRECT FLUORESCENT ANTIBODY TESTING, RAPID IMMUNOCHROMATOGRAPHIC CARTRIDGE ASSAYS, MICROSCOPY WITH TRICHROME STAINING, ENZYME IMMUNOASSAYS, ENTEROSCOPY	TINIDAZOLE, METRONIDAZOLE, SECNIDAZOLE, ORNIDAZOLE, NITAZOXANIDE, PAROMOMYCIN, ALBENDAZOLE, MEBENDAZOLE, QUINACRINE, FURAZOLIDONE	IMPROVED SANITATION, BOILING WATER, HAND HYGIENE, PURIFY WILDERNESS WATER, WASH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES, KEEP YOUR MOUTH CLOSED UNDERWATER, USE BOTTLED WATER, PRACTICE SAFER SEX, FOOD HYGIENE, PROPER PUBLIC WATER TREATMENT	4, 20, 22
12	MONKEYPOX	ORTHOPOXVIRUS MONKEYPOX	HUMAN TO HUMAN, SEXUAL CONTACT, CONTACT WITH BODILY FLUID OF INFECTED, ZOOONOTIC	SMALL MAMMALS	YES	RASH, BLISTERS, FEVER, SWOLLEN LYMPH NODES, MUSCLE ACHES, SORE THROAT, PNEUMONIA, SEPSIS, ENCEPHALITIS, LOSS OF VISION	VIRAL DNA DETECTION, RT-PCR, TWO SWABS MUST BE COLLECTED FROM EACH LESION FOR ADDITIONAL TESTS, MPOX TEST	TECOVIRIMAT, CIDOFOVIR, VACCINIA IMMUNE GLOBULIN, SUPPORTIVE CARE	VACCINE, HAND WASHING, PPE, SOCIAL DISTANCING, COVERING RASH, AVOID CONTACT WITH INFECTED PERSONS, DONOT SCRATCH OR POP THE RASH, KEEP THE RASH CLEAN AND DRY, WEAR MASK, EAT HEALTHY AND DRINK A LOT OF WATER, DISINFECTANT USAGE, AVOID SHARING ITEMS WITH INFECTED PERSON	
13	MARBURG VIRUS DISEASE	MARBURG VIRUS	ZOOONOTIC, HUMAN TO HUMAN TRANSMISSION (BODILY FLUIDS)	FRUIT BATS	NO	FEVER, HEADACHE, CHILLS, FATIGUE, NAUSEA, VOMITING, DIARRHOEA, PHARYNGITIS, MACULOPAPULAR RASH, ABDOMINAL PAIN, CONJUNCTIVITIS, MALAISE, DYSPNEA, EDEMA, EXANTHEMA,	RT-PCR, BLOOD TEST, ANTIBODY DETECTION, ANTIGEN TESTING, VIRUS ISOLATION BY CELL CULTURE	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	PPE, STERILIZATION, DISINFECTION, AVOID CONTACT WITH INFECTED PERSONS AND PERSONS WHO DIED OF IT	9, 22

						ENCEPHALITIS, DELIRIUM, APATHY, CONFUSION, AGGRESSION, HEMORRHAGIC SYMPTOMS, BLOODY STOOLS, ECCHYMOSIS, BLOOD LEAKAGE FROM VENIPUNCTURE SITES, MUCOSAL AND VISCERAL HEMORRHAGING, HEMATEMESIS, MYALGIA, FIBROMYALGIA, HEPATITIS, ASTHENIA, OCULAR SYMPTOMS, PSYCHOSIS, OBTUNDATION, COMA, CONVULSIONS, DIFFUSE COAGULOPATHY, METABOLIC DISTURBANCES, SHOCK				
14	POWASSAN VIRUS ENCEPHALITIS AND RHOMBENCEPHALITIS	POWASSAN VIRUS	ZOONOTIC, VECTOR	MAMMAL, MICE, BAT	NO	MENINGOENCEPHALITIS AND RHOMBENCEPHALITIS(RARE) (FEVER, HEADACHE, NAUSEA, CONFUSION, WEAKNESS, SEIZURES, APHASIA, CRANIAL NERVE PALSIES, PARESIS, ALTERED MENTAL STATUS)	BLOOD TESTS, LUMBAR PUNCTURE, IMAGING, ANTIBODY DETECTION, NEUTRALIZATION ASSAYS	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	(AVOID TICKS) USAGE OF REPELLANTS, CLOTHING, AVOID BUSHY AREAS	14,15, 22
15	BORRELIA MIYAMOTOI DISEASE/HARD TICK RELAPSING FEVER	BORRELIA MIYAMOTOI	ZOONOTIC, VECTOR,	MICE, VOLES, RATS	NO	MENINGOENCEPHALITIS(RARE); FLU-LIKE SYMPTOMS, FEVER, NAUSEA, VOMITING, HEADACHE, ARTHRALGIAS, MALAISE, MYALGIA, ELEVATED LIVER	PCR, ANTIBODY DETECTION, BLOOD TESTS, URINE TESTS, LIVER FUNCTION TESTS, COMPLETE BLOOD CELL COUNT, MICROSCOPY WITH STAINING, SERODIAGNOSIS,	DOXYCYCLINE, CEFTRIAXONE, AMOXICILLIN	(AVOID TICKS) USAGE OF REPELLANTS, CLOTHING, AVOID BUSHY AREAS	

						TRANSAMI NASES, THROMBO CYTOPENI A, LEUKOPEN IA				
16	HEARTL AND VIRUS DISEAS E	HEART LAND VIRUS	ZOONOTIC, VECTOR	WHITE TAILED DEER	NO	FEVER, LETHARGY , HEADACHE , MUSCLE PAIN, LOSS OF APPETITE, NAUSEA, DIARRHOE A, WEIGHT LOSS, JOINT PAIN, LOW WBC COUNT, EASY BRUISING DUE TO LOW PLATELET COUNT, ELEVATED LIVER TRANSAMI NASES	RTPCR, ANTIBODY TITERS, ANTIBODY DETECTION, NEUTRALIZA TION ASSAYS, WHITE BLOOD CELL COUNT, PLATELET COUNT, LIVER ENZYME LEVEL	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	(AVOID TICKS) USAGE OF REPELLANTS, CLOTHING, AVOID BUSHY AREAS	14
17	TICK BORNE RELAPSI NG FEVER	BORRE LIA HERMS II	ZOONOTIC, VECTOR	SMALL RODENTS, MAMMALS, WHITE TAILED DEER	NO	FEVER, HEADACHE , MYALGIA, NAUSEA, VOMITING, ARTHALGI A, CHILLS, ERYTHEM A MIGRANS, DIARRHOE A, SWEATING, FATIGUE, ABDOMINA L PAIN, MALAISE, ANOREXIA, PHOTOPHO BIA, RASH, RIGORS, JAUNDICE, ASTHENIA, ACHES, SPLENOME GALY, NECK STIFFNESS, LYMPHAD ENOPATHY , DIZZINESS, TACHYCAR DIA, NACK PAIN, EPISTAXIS, SUBCONJU CTIVAL HEMORRH AGE, HEPATOME GALY, LETHARGY , BLURRED VISION, CONFUSIO N, EYE PAIN, LOSS OF APPETITE, SORE THROAT, CHEST PAIN,	MICROSCOPI C EXAMINATIO N OF BLOOD SMEARS, PCR, CULTURE, SEROLOGY TESTING, ANIMAL INOCUATION, ANTIBODY DETECTION, ANTIGEN DETECTION	TETRACYCLI NES, B- LACTAMS, MACROLIDS, ERYTHROMY CIN, DOXYCYCLI NE, PENICILLIN, CHLORAMPH ENICOL	(AVOID TICKS) USAGE OF REPELLANTS, CLOTHING, AVOID BUSHY AREAS, (AVOID RODENTS)	14, 24

						<p> IRRITABILITY, DYSPNOEA, MACULAR RASH, MENINGISM, DISTURBED GAIT, ESCHAR, PETECHIAE, MEMORY DEFICIT, PRURITUS, RHINORRHOEA, SLEEP DISTURBANCES, CONVULSIONS, DEHYDRATION, DIFFICULT HEARING, DIPLOPIA, DYSMETRIA, DYSURIA, FLANK PAIN, HALLUCINATION, HAND NUMBNESS, LOWER LIMB PAIN, LIMB PAIN, PHONOPHOBIA, SYNCOPE; MENINGITIS, IRITIS, ACUTE RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME, UVEITIS, FACIAL PALSY, ENCEPHALITIS, ACUTE RENAL FAILURE, ANGINA PECTORIS, COMA, FACIOBRANCHIAL HEMIPARESIS, CAVERNOUS SINUS THROMBOSIS, DISSEMINATED INTRAVASCULAR COAGULATION, CRANIAL POLYNEURITIS, ENDOTHELAMITIS, HEARING LOSS, HEPATITIS, MYOCARDITIS, NEPHRITIS, PNEUMONIA, SEPTIC SHOCK, NEONATAL </p>				
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						ASPHYXIA, THROMBO PHLEBITIS, SUBARCHA NOIDAL HEMORRH AGE; THROMBO CYTOPENI A, LEUCOCYT OSIS, ANAEMIA, PROTEINU RIA, TROPONIN EMIA, ELEVATED ALANINE AMINOTRA NSFERASE, ALKALINE PHOSPHAT ASE, ASPARTAT E TRANSAMI NASE, CREATINE KINASE, C- REACTIVE PROTEIN, ERYTHROC YTE SEDIMENT ATION RATE, GAMMA- GLUTAMY LTRANSFE RASE, LACTATE DEHYDRO GENASE				
18	HUMAN MONOC YTIC EHRLIC HIOSIS	EHRLI CHIA CHAFF EENSIS	ZOONOTIC	WHITE TAILED DEER, GOATS, DOGS, RACOONS, COYOTES	NO	FEVER, HEADACHE , MALAISE, LOW BACK PAIN, GASTROIN TESTINAL SYMPTOMS , MYALGIAS, ARTHALGI AS, COUGHING , PHARYNGI TIS, DIARRHOE A, VOMITING, ABDOMINA L PAIN, CHANGE IN MENTAL STATUS	PCR, SEROLOGIC TESTING, BLOOD CELL COUNT, ANTIBODY DETECTION, ANTIBODY TITLERS, WESTERN BLOTTING, STAINING AND MICROSCOPY , ISOLATION OF PATHOGEN	TETRACYCLI NE(DOXYCY CLINE)	(AVOID TICK BITES) CLOTHING, REPELLANTS USAGE, AVOID TICK PREVALENT AREA	14
19	ANAPLA SMOSIS	ANAPL ASMA PHAGO CYTOP HLIU M	ZOONOTIC	SHEEPS	NO	JAUNDICE, WEIGHT LOSS, DIARRHOE A, PALENESS OF THE SKIN, AGGRESSI VE BEHAVIOU R, HIGH FEVER, LOW WBC CELLS, LOW PLATELETS , ELEVATED	CULTURE, HISTOPATHO LOGY, SEROLOGY TESTING, PCR, BLOOD CELL COUNT, BLOOD TEST, ISOLATION OF PATHOGEN FROM BLOOD SMEARS, COMPLETE METABOLIC PROFILE, ANTIBODY DETECTION, MICROSCOPY	TETRACYCLI NE, IMIDOCARB, DOXYCYCLI NE, AMOXICILLI N, CEFUROXIME , RIFAMPIN	TICK CONTROL, TESTING FOR DISEASE IN RUMINANTS AND HUMANS, IMPROVED SANITATION, (AVOID TICK BITES) CLOTHING, REPELLANTS USAGE, AVOID TICK PREVALENT AREA	6, 14

						LIVER ENZYME, ANAEMIA, BLOOD IN THE URINE, ANOREXIA, PALENESS OF THE EYES	IMMUNOSTAINING			
20	BRUCELLA	BRUCELLA	ZOOONOTIC, INGESTION OF UNPASTEURIZED MILK	SHEEP, GOAT, CATTLE	NO	FEVER, SWEATING, ARTHRALGIA, MYALGIA, LOW NUMBER OF WHITE BLOOD CELLS AND RED BLOOD CELLS, ELEVATION OF LIVER ENZYMES, NAUSEA, VOMITING, DECREASED APPETITE, UNINTENTIONAL WEIGHT LOSS, ABDOMINAL PAIN, CONSTIPATION, DIARRHEA, AN ENLARGED LIVER, LIVER INFLAMMATION, LIVER ABSCESS, AN ENLARGED SPLEEN, ARTHRITIS, SPONDYLITIS, THROMBOCYTOPENIA, MENINGITIS, UVEITIS, OPTIC NEURITIS, ENDOCARDITIS, NEUROBRUCELLOSIS, OSTEOMYELITIS, SPONDYLODISCITIS, SACROILIITIS, ORCHITIS	BLOOD CULTURE, DETECTION OF ANTIBIOTICS, COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT, INFLAMMATORY MARKERS, LIVER ENZYMES, CULTURE, SEROLOGY TESTING, PCR, BIOPSY, IMAGING, ANTIGEN DETECTION, CULTURE	TETRACYCLINES, RIFAMPICIN, AMINOGLYCOSIDES, STREPTOMYCIN, GENTAMICIN, DOXYCYCLINE, CO-TRIMOXAZOLE, CIPROFLOXACIN, TRIMETHOPRIMSULFAMETHOXAZOLE	COOK FOOD PROPERLY, AVOID UNPASTEURIZED MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS, WEAR APPROPRIATE PPE WHILE DEALING WITH ANIMALS, VACCINATE ANIMALS	12
21	FASCIOULOSIS	FASCIOULOSIS, FASCIOULOSIS	FOODBORNE, ZOOONOSIS	PIGS	NO	ACUTE PHASE: KILLS THE LIVER'S CELLS AND CAUSES INTENSE INTERNAL BLEEDING. TYPICAL SYMPTOMS INCLUDE FEVER, NAUSEA, A SWOLLEN LIVER,	BLOOD EOSINOPHIL COUNT >500-1000 PER ML OF BLOOD, ULTRASOUND OR COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY SCANS, EGGS IN STOOL SAMPLES, ORMSPECIFIC ANTIBODIES	TRICLABENDAZOLE	FOOD HYGIENE, AVOID RAW FOODS, EAT BOILED FOOD	22

						SKIN RASHES AND EXTREME ABDOMINAL PAIN; CHRONIC PHASE: INTERMITTENT PAIN, JAUNDICE AND ANAEMIA. PANCREATITIS, GALLSTONES AND BACTERIAL SUPER-INFECTIONS MAY ALSO OCCUR. PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC INFECTIONS EXPERIENCE HARDENING OF THE LIVER (FIBROSIS) AS A RESULT OF THE LONG-TERM INFLAMMATION.	IN SERUM SAMPLES OR WORM-SPECIFIC ANTIGENS IN SERUM OR STOOL SAMPLES			
22	PSEUDOMONAS TRUNCATUM - HEPATOBILIARY INFECTIONS	PSEUDOMONAS TRUNCATUM	FOODBORNE, ZOONOSIS	SEALS	NO	FEVER; ABDOMINAL PAIN; DIARRHEA, VOMITING, DECREASED APPETITE, LISTLESSNESS AND WEIGHT LOSS	LIVER PATHOLOGY, SCANNING OF ABDOMINAL	NO SPECIFICALLY ESTABLISHED DRUG	FOOD HYGIENE, AVOID RAW FOODS, EAT BOILED FOOD	23
23	HANTAVIRUS PULMONARY SYNDROME (HPS)	HANTAVIRUS	BREATHING CONTAMINATED AIR, VECTOR, ZOONOTIC	RODENTS, SHREWS, MOLES, BATS	YES	HANTAVIRUS PULMONARY SYNDROME (HPS): FATIGUE, FEVER, MUSCLE ACHES, ESPECIALLY IN THE LARGE MUSCLE GROUPS LIKE THE THIGHS, HIPS, BACK, AND SOMETIMES SHOULDER S, HEADACHE S, DIZZINESS, CHILLS, ABDOMINAL PROBLEMS, LIKE NAUSEA, VOMITING, DIARRHEA, AND	BLOOD TEST, VIRUS ANTIBODIES, ABNORMALLY LOW AMOUNT OF PLATELETS	NOT SPECIFIC (SUPPORTIVE CARE)	RODENT CONTROL	19, 16, 26

						ABDOMINAL PAIN				
24	EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE	EBOLA VIRUS	EATING INFECTED ANIMALS, BODY FLUIDS OF AN INFECTED PERSON SUCH AS SALIVA, URINE, FAECES OR SEMEN, THINGS THAT HAVE THE BODY FLUIDS OF AN INFECTED PERSON LIKE CLOTHES OR SHEETS	FRUIT BATS	YES	FEELING TIRED, HEADACHE, MUSCLE AND JOINT PAIN, EYE PAIN AND VISION PROBLEMS, WEIGHT GAIN, BELLY PAIN AND LOSS OF APPETITE, HAIR LOSS AND SKIN PROBLEMS, TROUBLE SLEEPING, MEMORY LOSS, HEARING LOSS, DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY, LONG-LASTING EFFECTS INCLUDE: HEADACHE, SKIN PEELING, VISION PROBLEMS (BLURRED VISION, LIGHT SENSITIVITY, VISION LOSS), NUMBNESS AND TINGLING (PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY), EYE PAIN OR REDNESS, MUSCLE AND JOINT PAIN, STOMACH PAIN	ANTIBODY-CAPTURE ENZYME-LINKED IMMUNOSORBENT ASSAY (ELISA), ANTIGEN-TEST, SERUM NEUTRALIZATION TEST, RT-PCR, CULTURE TEST	MONOCLONAL ANTIBODY TREATMENTS: INMAZEB & EBANGA AND INTRAVENOUS (IV) FLUIDS (IF REQUIRED)	ERVEBO VACCINE, USE PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT, AVOID CONTACT WITH ANYTHING THAT MAY HAVE TOUCHED INFECTED BODY FLUIDS, AVOID TOUCHING THE BODY OF SOMEONE WHO DIED FROM EBOLA, VOID CONTACT WITH BODY FLUIDS AND TISSUES OF INFECTED ANIMALS, MONITOR YOURSELF FOR SYMPTOMS FOR 21 DAYS, DON'T EAT BUSH MEAT, USE BOILED WATER / FOOD, ISOLATE YOURSELF, ISOLATE THE INFECTED PEOPLE.	22, 9

CONCLUSION:

The governing bodies shall frame policy framework, implementation road map and monitoring the policy implementation on climate change. People see it as floods, tornadoes, tsunamis, droughts, heatwaves, etc. and they need more education about diseases and climate change. It affects population unequally, but still all are affected in any one way at least. It can be concluded that requirement of various expert committees and their inputs are required for development of broader roadmap to address climate induced communicable diseases. More preventive strategies must be considered. Dormant and potent diseases in nature must be identified and treatment and prevention strategies must be devised. Caution to be exercised during the application of the Symptom, Diagnosis, Treatment outlined in the treatment section of this paper.

Acknowledgements:

Author would like to thank his parents, grandparents and his younger brother Sriram C for their continuous support and motivation.

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